

“A Study on Customer’s Perception Towards E-Vehicles:”-In Reference To Meerut

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ABSTRACT

This research article examines consumer’s perception towards E-Vehicle which focuses on factors like environmental impact , cost savings , charging infrastructure , and government policies. The research aims to identify barriers to adoption of E -vehicles. The rapid growth of electric vehicles (EVs) has been a significant trend in the automotive industry. Electric vehicles (EVs) offer a promising solution to combat environmental issues by reducing carbon emissions.

INTRODUCTION:

In the modern world, with everyone's hectic schedules and always rushing around, we all need the reliable assistance of our vehicles. The first thing that comes to mind when we consider going outside is ‘driving’ as it's a highly practical way to get where we're going and it also frees up a lot of time and efforts from our busy schedules.

As almost everyone owns a vehicle these days, petrol and diesel are major fuel consumption for these vehicles. Since everyone is aware of motor vehicles, whether two- or four-wheeled, generate hazardous gasses including CO₂, CO, NO_x, and other air contaminants, which have a major negative influence on the environment and human health. However, the concern over greenhouse gas emissions, their negative effects, and fuel depletion forces humanity to start looking for alternate approaches. Car emissions can lead to short-term issues as well as long-term ones. There are several ways in which the contaminants listed above can be detrimental to our environment and health. The following is a list of some of the negative effects:

Global warming: The pollutants released by vehicles are one of the main causes of global warming, despite the fact that there are many other forces at play. Gases like carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide are released when fossil fuels burn. Other greenhouse gases, such as hydrocarbons, which are indirect greenhouse gases, are also released. The environment is impacted by these gases, which cause global warming.

Water, soil, and air pollution: The consequences of vehicle pollution are felt strongly in the air, water, and soil. Depletion of the ozone layer puts the planet at danger of being exposed to the sun's damaging UV rays. When sulfur and nitrogen oxides mix with precipitation, acid rain is created.

Risks to health: Car pollution is the cause of many health risks, ranging from cancer to respiratory conditions. It is also to blame for the weakened immunity. As a result, there is a greater chance of contracting various illnesses and consequences.

In this context, E-Vehicles plays the major role by lowering the carbon emissions. EVs are innovative kind of vehicles which rely on electricity rather than gasoline, diesel, or other conventional fuels. Also, E-Vehicles are not harmful for the environment and air.

If we talk about EV then, **Scooters India PVT Ltd** invented the first electric vehicle, which was three-wheeler named VIKRAM SAFA in 1996. Which was the success as it sold the approx. 400 vehicles.

Here is a brief list of the various kinds of battery electric vehicles, or BEVs.

- Electrical vehicles for the neighborhood: compact cars with a very short range (less than 25 km)
- City electric vehicles: compact cars with a short range (less than 50 km)
- Performance battery-electric cars: these have a range of between 100 and 600 km, making them the match for traditional passenger cars.

The government also implements several programs to control the use of EVs in the economy, such as in 2013 National Electric Mobility Mission Plan (NEMMP). Through the national promotion of hybrid and electric vehicles, it seeks to create fuel security for the nation and the Faster Adoption and Manufacturing of (Hybrid &) Electric Vehicles (FAME) scheme in 2015.

Also, the '**Make in India**' initiative was launched in 2014 by the Indian government with the aim of promoting domestic manufacturing and boosting economic growth..

Initiative took towards E-Vehicles proved successfully as it attracts the foreign investment and creating high job opportunities in different sectors, including EV industries.

Electric vehicles are the way of the future; they can preserve the environment and save energy, both of which are crucial for our future. generation. This research will assist electric vehicle dealers in making decisions about opening an outlet and will also provide insight into the adoption rate of these vehicles in comparison to combustion vehicles in daily life.

Following are some vehicles producers of India

Tata Motors,

JBM Auto,

Olectra Greentech,

Mahindra Electric mobility,

Ola Electric Mobility,

Ashok Leyland Electric,

Hyundai,

Hero Electric,

Menza Motors,

Lohia Auto,

Kia Motors,

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Dr. M. Kalimuthu, Sugeerthi AV (2023) : With an increase of 9% in sales , electric vehicles industry is growing at a fastpace due to its environment friendly and cost effective nature. Advancement in battery technology and faster charging times has led to nearly double sales in last two years. though there will be some hurdles to overcome, but electric vehicle market is not going to slow down and soon electric vehicles will be a common sight on our roads.

Rahul Pauer, Raj Shree Ranjan, Dr. Paresh Patel (2024) : The subsidy policy for electric vehicle in Gujarat promotes the adoption of electric vehicles by providing financial incentives and a robust charging infrastructure. Using electric vehicle and phasing out polluting vehicles, not only saves money but also contributes to a healthier and cleaner environment

Dr R Muthukrishnan , Perezhil Prakash R , Naveen Rajkumar M , Ranjithvel A , Akhil C :

There is a positive perception of customers towards electric vehicles. Customers have started to comprehend the benefits of electric vehicles over traditional vehicles. The current automobile market holds a huge share of EV industry as the quality of products has improved as there have been significant technological advancements.

Ms. Monika (2018) : This study aims to comprehend whether the customers are willing to adopt electric vehicles even after its several obstacles and opportunities. Through this study we want to know whether the customers are ready to do their bit towards sustainable environment.

Tiziana Campisia , Dario Ticalia , Matteo Ignacolob , Giovanni Tesorieria , Giuseppe Inturric , Vincenza Torrisib : This analysis is a survey for further research in travel habits and choice of transport in relation to type of fuel. The responses of the survey are influenced by the infrastructural factors, policy implemented and socio economic factors.

Sita Mishra, Gunjan Malhotra : This study featured that there is a positive correlation in purchase intention and performance features for EVs. Though the availability of EVs is in budding stage still it provide a lot of superior and technical features in comparison to traditional vehicles. Indian markets should highlight performance feature as unique selling point while promoting EVs.

Prof Debasish Rout, Dr Somabhusana Janakiballav Mishra, Dr Ranjan Kumar Kantha Suprakash Pal : HEVs are configured to obtain the benefits of both IC engines and electric motors and providing fuel efficiency and increased power. Power transmission using chain wheels and freewheels is incredibly reliable and reasonably priced.. The only disadvantage of electric power is that it is not a good option for long distance travel. The costs of HEVs is more than the traditional vehicles but they are more useful in minimising overall fuel consumption and their exhaust emission is also less

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the extent of customer familiarity with electric vehicles (EVs).

2. To explore the impact of electric vehicles (EVs) on the environment.
3. To study the satisfaction level of consumers.
4. To examine what motivates people to purchase electric vehicles

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Data Collection :The data collection approach that will be used is the Primary approach; the sample respondents will be selected by a snowball sampling technique using a schedule and an online questionnaire.

Sampling Design: A sampling design is a definite plan for a obtaining a sample from a given population. The sampling approach will be use in this study is **snowball sampling**.

Area of Population: Dehradun will be my area of population.

Sample size:the sample size is the measure of the number of individual samples used in the experiment. My sample size is limited to 150 to 200 users (approx.).

LIMITATIONS:

- 1.The area of study is limited to researcher.
2. The respondents limit not exceed to 200 which is very limited.
- 3.Feedback of customers may be biased.
- 4.The attitude and the behavior of customer may affect their Reponses.

FINDINGS:

A study was conducted for a total of 100 people in the region of Meerut, U.P.

- 1.66% of the respondents were male and 34% were female.
2. Among the respondents 48% were of age group of 16-21 , 29% were from 22-27 years , 13% were from 27-30 years and 10% were above 32 years.
3. The study showed that 76%of the respondents owned a vehicle and 24% didn't owned a vehicle.

4. Out of the 76% of people owning a vehicle majority of the people (80%) owned a petrol vehicle, 8% owned a electric vehicle , 6% owned a diesel vehicle and 4% owned a hybrid vehicle
5. The study showed that 91% were people aware of E vehicles
- 6.36% of the population had very positive perceptions of E vehicles.

CONCLUSION:

To conclude , the study threw light upon the various factors on which the consumers perception towards e vehicles is based. Majority of population is sensitive towards environment and therefore, consider environmental factors as the main reason to purchase e vehicles . On the other hand people are also considerate about the cost savings on the fuels .

Moreover, people are also hesitant to purchase e vehicles due to limited charging stations and lack of knowledge.

The scope of E-vehicles is very wide on Indian markets. Therefore, government should take steps towards enhancing the charging infrastructure and creating awareness among people about e vehicles.

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